

CONSTRAINT TO WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION IN COMMUNITY AND SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT PROJECTS (CSDP) IN AKWA IBOM STATE

Rhoda Ohunene Ajayi¹

Emmanuel Edet Umoh²

Unyime Robson Etuk³

^{1,2,&3}Department of Agricultural Extension and Rural Development,
University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Corresponding author:

unyimeetuk2021@gmail.com

unyimeetuk@uniuyo.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study examined the factors affecting women's participation in Community and Social Development Projects (CSDPs) in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Despite the recognized importance of women's involvement, participation remains suboptimal. A multi-stage sampling procedure was used to select 150 women beneficiaries from three Local Government Areas (LGAs). Data were collected through structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including factor analysis. Results show that 26.7% of women had low participation, 56.7% had moderate participation, and only 16.6% had high participation in CSDP activities. The principal factors affecting participation were family support and financial barriers (18.2%), health and educational barriers (15.7%), safety and project relevance concerns (13.8%), and time and marital constraints (12.4%), which together accounted for a total variance of 88.3% in women's participation in CSDP. The study concludes that enhancing family and community support, and offering flexible participation options can significantly increase women's participation in CSDPs, thereby fostering more effective and sustainable community development in Akwa Ibom State.

Keywords: Women's participation, Community and Social Development Projects (CSDP)

INTRODUCTION

Community and Social Development Projects (CSDPs) are essential for improving living standards in developing countries like Nigeria, addressing challenges such as poverty, inadequate infrastructure, and limited access to healthcare and education (Ochepo, Ejembi, and Jiriko, 2019; Yusuf, Adekunmi, and Ayanda, 2020). These projects aim to foster sustainable development through community-driven initiatives. Women, who form a significant portion of Akwa Ibom State's population, are crucial to the success of these projects. They are often primary caregivers and household managers, bringing unique perspectives that enhance project effectiveness and sustainability. Their participation leads to inclusive decision-making, better project outcomes, and stronger community cohesion

(Ajayi and Okunlola, 2020; Jimmy and Olsson, 2023).

Despite the recognized importance of women's participation in CSDPs, their involvement remains suboptimal in many regions, including Akwa Ibom State. Previous studies have identified socio-cultural, economic, and institutional barriers to women's engagement in CSDPs in various Nigerian states. Ajayi *et al.* (2021) found that socio-cultural norms and economic constraints were significant barriers in Ondo State, while Ajayi and Okunlola (2020) highlighted similar issues affecting women's perceptions of CSDPs' impacts on their livelihoods. However, these studies do not address the specific context of Akwa Ibom State. In Akwa Ibom State, research by Akpan (2022) and Tom and Attai (2014) has focused on broader community development and government empowerment programs but not specifically on women's participation in CSDPs. This gap in research needs addressing to develop effective strategies for increasing women's involvement in community development initiatives.

Ekpenyong *et al.* (2023) identified socio-cultural barriers to women's participation in community projects in Northern Cross River State, suggesting similar issues may exist in Akwa Ibom State. Although Etuk *et al.* (2019) discussed socio-cultural constraints in Akwa Ibom, their study did not focus exclusively on CSDPs, leaving a gap in understanding the distinct challenges within these projects. It is against this backdrop that this study is carried out to address the following questions: (i) what is the current level of women's participation in Community and Social Development Projects (CSDPs) in Akwa Ibom State? (ii) what constraints to women's participation in CSDPs in Akwa Ibom State?

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, which spans approximately 7,246 square kilometers and has a population exceeding 5 million. Positioned between latitudes 4° 33' and 5° 33' North, and longitudes 7° 25' and 8° 25' East, the state is known for its cultural diversity, with prominent ethnic groups including the Ibibio, Annang, Oron, and Igbo (Etuk and Umoh, 2014). This diversity enriches the state's cultural landscape, contributing to its identity as a significant cultural hub within Nigeria.

The study population comprised all women who have benefited from CSDP in Akwa Ibom State, encompassing women from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds in both urban and rural communities. A multi-stage sampling procedure was employed to ensure representative participation. First, 25 LGAs where CSDP interventions had been implemented were purposively selected. From these, three LGAs; Abak, Itu, and Urue Offong/Oruko were randomly chosen to minimize bias and enhance generalizability. Within each selected LGA, three communities that had significantly benefited from CSDP were purposively chosen. Finally, convenience sampling was used to select twenty-five women beneficiaries from each community, resulting in a total sample size of 150 respondents. A structured questionnaire was designed to capture the study's objectives, measuring the extent of women's participation in CSDP and the factors affecting their participation. Participation levels were rated on a 4-point Likert scale across 10 areas, categorized into low, moderate, and high participation based on scores ranging from 0 to 30. Factors affecting participation were assessed using a 4-point Likert scale, with factor analysis revealing seven principal factors. The KMO measure was 0.812, and Bartlett's Test of Sphericity confirmed data suitability for factor analysis. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 22,

employing descriptive and inferential statistics. Frequency counts, percentages, and means were used to achieve the first objective, while factor analysis was used to address the second objective.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Level of Participation of respondents in Community and Social Development Projects

The results indicate varying levels of participation among women in Community and Social Development Projects (CSDP) in Akwa Ibom State. The categorization of respondents' participation levels reveals that 26.7% of women had low participation, 56.7% had moderate participation, and only 16.6% exhibited high participation in CSDP activities as indicated in Table 1. The findings highlight several critical implications. The low to moderate participation levels in most CSDP activities align with findings from other studies, such as Ajayi *et al.* (2021), which observed similar trends in Ondo State. This suggests that systemic issues affecting women's engagement in community projects might be widespread across different regions in Nigeria. For instance, Ajayi *et al.* (2021) pointed out that socio-cultural constraints, lack of awareness, and inadequate mobilization efforts are significant barriers to women's participation, which resonates with the current study's observation of higher participation in awareness creation activities compared to other project phases.

The results also echo the conclusions of Ekpenyong *et al.* (2023), who identified socio-cultural factors as critical inhibitors to women's involvement in community development projects. The relatively higher participation in awareness creation activities could indicate that while women are willing to engage in informational and preparatory phases of projects, deeper involvement in decision-making and implementation phases remains limited due to enduring cultural and structural barriers. This pattern is further supported by the work of Etuk *et al.* (2019), which highlighted how socio-cultural constraints, such as traditional gender roles and limited access to resources, significantly hinder women's full participation in community development.

Conversely, the findings of this study diverge from those of Akpan (2022), who reported higher levels of women's participation in rural community projects in Akwa Ibom State, particularly in initiatives that had strong governmental support and targeted women empowerment. This discrepancy might be attributed to differences in the types of projects studied or the specific methodologies employed, suggesting the need for a nuanced understanding of the various factors that influence women's participation in different contexts.

Moreover, the relatively high involvement in awareness creation activities, as seen in this study, may indicate that women are more actively engaged in initial stages of community projects but face significant drop-offs in participation as projects progress into more intensive phases. This trend is consistent with findings by Gyan *et al.* (2021), who noted that while women are often enthusiastic participants in the initial stages of community development projects, their involvement tends to wane due to structural and operational challenges.

Table 1: Categorization of respondent's level of Participation in CSDP

Categories	Participation Scale Score	Frequency	Percentage
Low Participation	0 – 10	40	26.7
Moderate Participation	11 – 21	85	56.7
High Participation	22 – 32	25	16.6
Total		150	100

Source: Field data (2024)

Factors Affecting Women's Participation in CSDP

The analysis of factors affecting women's participation in Community and Social Development Projects (CSDP) in Akwa Ibom State highlights several dimensions, ranging from family and financial barriers to health, confidence, safety, and support issues as indicated in Table 2. Lack of Family Support and Financial Barriers, which account for 18.2% of the variance, represent significant challenges for women. These findings indicate that the lack of family support and the financial burden of participating in community projects are key deterrents. This result is consistent with studies by Luftu-ul-Hasnaen *et al.* (2023), which emphasize the importance of family backing and economic stability in empowering rural women through development initiatives. The role of family support, particularly for married women balancing household responsibilities, is critical. Furthermore, the need for financial assistance highlights the economic challenges women face, as found by Okereke-Ejiogu *et al.* (2016), who identified similar financial constraints in Imo State, Nigeria.

Health and Educational Barriers, accounting for 15.7% of the variance, suggest that women's participation is hindered by health issues and limited educational opportunities. This aligns with the findings of Firdoos *et al.* (2023), who noted the impact of health challenges on women's ability to engage in community activities. Similarly, education barriers, particularly difficulties in understanding project objectives, reflect the need for better educational support, as observed by De Ravindranath *et al.* (2021), who identified the critical role of education in improving women's confidence to contribute to community development.

Safety and Project Relevance Concerns, which explain 13.8% of the variance, emphasize that women often feel unsafe when participating in community projects, or perceive these projects as irrelevant to their needs. This finding is consistent with Pradhan *et al.* (2023), who noted the importance of aligning community projects with women's interests to ensure their engagement. The perception of personal safety and project relevance is crucial, as echoed by Iuliano *et al.* (2023), who found that successful interventions must resonate with local needs.

Perceived Impact and Role Models, accounting for 12.4% of the variance, highlight the influence of perceived benefits and the availability of female role models. Women's belief in the limited impact of their participation diminishes their motivation to engage, a challenge also identified by Kobani (2020) in Rivers State, Nigeria. The lack of visible female role models compounds this issue, further discouraging participation. Visible leadership figures are essential for inspiring women to take active roles in community development.

Time and Marital Constraints, which explain 10.6% of the variance, reflect the significant influence of time availability and marital status on women's ability to participate in

CSDP projects. The time demands of household responsibilities and the cultural restrictions tied to marital status limit women's involvement. This resonates with the findings of Etuk *et al.* (2019), who discussed the socio-cultural constraints women face in balancing domestic duties with community engagement. Cultural practices that restrict women's mobility or participation in public activities also contribute to these barriers.

Community Support and Leadership Encouragement, which account for 8.9% of the variance, stress the importance of encouragement from community leaders and the availability of training opportunities for women. As observed by Umar *et al.* (2024), leadership support is critical to boosting women's participation. Training programs aimed at building women's skills are essential for fostering their active involvement, a point also highlighted by Adejoh (2015) in his study on community development in Nigeria.

Respect and Awareness Issues, explaining 8.7% of the variance, focus on the respect afforded to women's contributions and awareness of the benefits of participation. These factors align with the findings of Odenigbo *et al.* (2022), who identified the importance of respect for women's roles in ensuring the success of community projects. Although awareness of the CSDP in Akwa Ibom State was found to be moderate, some women still face challenges in understanding the broader benefits of their participation. Uzoagu (2019) similarly noted that raising awareness is critical to improving women's involvement in development initiatives.

Together, these factors provide a comprehensive understanding of the barriers and enablers influencing women's participation in CSDP projects in Akwa Ibom State. Addressing these issues, particularly through financial support, health interventions, and community leadership, will be crucial for increasing women's involvement and ensuring the success of development projects.

Table 2: Component correlation matrix of constraints to Women's Participation in CSDP

Factors affecting Women's Participation in CSDP	Fac. 1	Fac. 2	Fac. 3	Fac. 4	Fac. 5	Fac. 6	Fac. 7	Cum
Lack of family support for participation	0.75							0.75
Financial challenges for women participating in projects	0.68							0.70
Lack of confidence in contributing to community projects	0.69							0.68
Health issues prevent me from taking part in community projects				0.72				0.72
Educational difficulties in understanding community projects				0.69				0.73
Exclusion from decision-making processes				0.71				0.76
Feeling unsafe when participating in community projects							0.70	0.68
Community projects do not align with my personal interests							0.67	0.66
Projects do not meet the needs of women in the community						0.66		0.71
Perception of no positive changes from women's participation						0.68		0.69
Absence of female role models						0.76		0.74
Insufficient time to participate in community projects					0.67			0.68
Marital status prevents participation					0.74			0.67
Cultural practices prevent participation		0.70						0.69
Lack of encouragement from community leaders		0.66						0.65
Lack of training opportunities for women		0.65						0.74
Lack of respect for women's participation			0.68					0.71
Unawareness of the benefits of participating in community projects			0.71					0.67
Projects do not help improve my family's livelihood			0.74					0.66
Lack of family support for participation					0.73			0.69
Eigen Value	4.32	3.76	3.21	2.85	2.50	2.14	1.95	
Percentage (%) of Variation	18.2	15.7	13.8	12.4	10.6	8.9	8.7	
Cumulative Percentage	18.2	33.9	47.7	60.1	70.7	79.7	88.3	

KMO: 0.812, Bartlett's Test: Chi-Square = 2456.78, Sig. = 0.000

Source: Field data (2024)

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study underscore the critical need to address various barriers that impede women's participation in Community and Social Development Projects (CSDP) in Akwa Ibom State. The participation of women in these projects is essential for achieving sustainable community development, yet it remains constrained by several socio-cultural, economic, and institutional factors. The study revealed that while women show a relatively high level of involvement in awareness creation activities, their participation in decision-making and implementation phases is notably lower. This discrepancy highlights the enduring challenges that women face in engaging more deeply in CSDP activities.

The factor analysis identified seven principal barriers to women's participation: family support and financial barriers, health and educational barriers, safety and project relevance concerns, and time and marital constraints. These barriers collectively explain a significant portion of the variance in women's participation levels.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to enhance women's participation in CSDPs, the following recommendations are proposed based on the findings of this study:

- 1. Enhance Family and Community Support:** Efforts should be made to foster family and community support for women's involvement in CSDPs. This could include community sensitization programs that highlight the benefits of women's participation, as well as involving family members in discussions about the positive impacts of these projects on household welfare.
- 2. Promote Educational and Confidence-building Programs:** Educational initiatives aimed at building women's confidence and skills are essential. Workshops, training sessions, and mentorship programs can empower women with the knowledge and confidence needed to participate effectively in CSDPs. These programs should also address cultural and traditional norms that limit women's roles in decision-making processes.
- 3. Ensure Safety and Relevance of Projects:** Community projects should be designed to address the specific safety concerns of women and align with their interests and needs. This could involve incorporating women's input in the planning stages of projects to ensure that they are relevant and beneficial to their lives, thereby increasing their willingness to participate.
- 4. Provide Time and Resource Flexibility:** Recognizing the time constraints and marital obligations that many women face, CSDPs should offer flexible participation options. This could include scheduling meetings at convenient times for women, providing childcare support during project activities, and ensuring that projects are not overly demanding on women's time and resources.

By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can create a more inclusive environment that facilitates greater women's participation in Community and Social Development Projects, ultimately leading to more effective and sustainable community development outcomes in Akwa Ibom State.

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